

CONSTITUTION AS THE MAIN LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Translated from Latin, the word "constitutio" means "device". The Constitution is the Basic Law of our country. As a single political and legal document, it defines the basic principles of relations between a person, society and the state, the structure of state power, and enshrines the rights and freedoms of citizens that the state has taken under its protection.

Touching upon the question of the importance of the Constitution in the life of the country, first of all, it is necessary to realize the importance of the Basic Law. In the legal system of any country, the Basic Law is considered a normative legal document having the highest legal force. No law or other normative legal act may contradict the principles and norms of the Constitution. The Constitution provides a clear definition of the administrative-territorial and state structure, the powers of legislative, executive and judicial authorities, the functioning of the electoral system, the rights, freedoms and duties of citizens, the relationship between the individual and society, the State and citizens.

The Constitution is a solid legal basis for the successes and milestones achieved during the period of independence, and we are deeply aware of and appreciate all this.

The development strategy developed on the basis of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan has brought the country and society to a new level in a short time. Today, at the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, large-scale reforms are being carried out to form a New Uzbekistan. In the implementation of the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, our Basic Law is of unlimited importance, since the practical implementation of all seven directions of the Strategy is inextricably linked with the Constitution. In particular, the second direction of the Strategy provides for the transformation of the principles of justice and the rule of law into a fundamental and necessary condition for the development of the country, ensuring the principle of "In the name of human honor and dignity." The process of transition to the construction of a New Uzbekistan, of course, required an update of the Basic Law. When drafting the updated Constitution, the proposals of the people were taken into account, and the adoption of the draft Constitutional Law was carried out by referendum.

A referendum is a form of direct expression of the will of citizens, expressed in voting on the most significant issues in order to adopt laws or other decisions. A referendum differs from an election in that in this process, voting is not for a specific candidate, but for the solution of a certain issue, whether it is the adoption of a law, bill, Constitution or amendments to it.

The decision adopted at the referendum has the highest legal force and can be canceled or changed only by referendum.

It should be noted that during the preparation of the draft Constitution, the opinions and proposals of the people were studied in two stages. At the first stage, more than 60 thousand proposals on drafting the Constitution were received from citizens. At the second stage, the draft Constitution was submitted for public discussion. Almost 5 million citizens were acquainted with the project through the media and the Internet; more than 150 thousand expressed their opinions and suggestions.

During the development of the project, international legal documents and the experience of more than 190 States were studied.

In the new version of the Constitution of Uzbekistan, the number of articles has been increased from 128 to 155, the number of norms from 275 to 434. Conceptual changes have been made to 91 of the 128 articles. In general, the Constitution has been changed by 65 percent.

It should be noted with special pride that a number of resolutions and decrees have been adopted aimed at improving state-building, the judicial and legal system, liberalizing the economy, developing the social sphere, strengthening interethnic harmony and friendship, the work carried out according to these documents is rising to a qualitatively new level, which increases the confidence of our people in the future, further happy and a comfortable life.

The atmosphere of peace and generosity in our country, the solidarity and friendship of representatives of all nationalities and faiths are a vivid confirmation of this. In particular, Russian, Kazakh, Turkmen, Korean, and Ukrainian national cultural centers are effectively operating in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In the preservation and development of one’s native language, national traditions and customs by each nation, the legal guarantees enshrined in our Basic Law are of particular importance.

In conclusion, I would like to quote from the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at a meeting with members of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis, representatives of political parties and the public: “The most important thing is that now we will never turn away from the path of reforms, we will go forward and only forward on the basis of the new man–society–state system”.

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